

An examination of global citizenship education from the perspective of pre-service teachers

Erwin B. Berry, Rose-ann Sanchez Lozada-Calihat

Department of General Teacher Training, North Eastern Mindanao State University (NEMSU), Tandag City, Philippines

Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 30, 2024

Revised Jan 31, 2025

Accepted Mar 19, 2025

Keywords:

Attitudes

Curriculum

Global citizenship education

Knowledge

Skills

ABSTRACT

This study evaluates pre-service teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and confidence regarding global citizenship education (GCE) at North Eastern Mindanao State University (NEMSU)-Tandag Campus. Using a mixed-methods approach, which included qualitative and quantitative research paradigms, the study assessed participants' familiarity with GCE concepts, their perceptions of its importance, and their readiness to integrate global perspectives into classroom teaching. A survey method was employed to gather data, revealing that while some pre-service teachers were highly familiar with GCE, many reported varying levels of confidence in their ability to promote global issues and foster critical thinking. Key findings include a significant number of respondents feeling neutral about their preparedness and a need for more targeted professional development. The study contributes to understanding the gaps in current teacher training programs and emphasizes the necessity for integrating comprehensive GCE training. The results suggest that enhanced training and resources are crucial for improving pre-service teachers' confidence and effectiveness in teaching from a global perspective. Future research should focus on developing and evaluating interventions to address these gaps and explore effective strategies for GCE integration in diverse educational contexts.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Erwin B. Berry

Department of General Teacher Training, North Eastern Mindanao State University (NEMSU)

Barangay Rosario, Tandag City, Philippines

Email: eberry@nemsu.edu.ph

1. INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly interconnected world, global citizenship has gained prominence in educational discourses. Global citizenship education (GCE) empowers learners to engage with global challenges and develop a critical consciousness regarding their roles as global citizens [1]. For future educators, particularly pre-service teachers, GCE is vital as it equips them with the skills necessary to address both local and global issues, fostering critical thinking and cultural awareness [2]. Higher global citizenship competency among pre-service teachers is linked to their ability to promote global citizenship effectively in classrooms, with knowledge, skills, and attitudes being significant factors [3].

Despite the growing emphasis on GCE, many pre-service teachers lack adequate exposure to the principles and practices required to effectively implement GCE in their future classrooms. Current teacher education programs often fail to provide the necessary global perspectives, resulting in a gap between the ideal of GCE and the actual preparedness of teachers to integrate these principles into their teaching [4], [5]. As a result, pre-service teachers are not sufficiently equipped to foster the global awareness, critical thinking, and ethical decision-making needed to address pressing global challenges such as environmental degradation, social inequalities, and conflict resolution.

One of the critical challenges in preparing pre-service teachers for GCE is that many teacher education programs still treat global citizenship as an optional or peripheral part of their curricula rather than a core component of teacher training [6]. Moreover, while there has been a call to integrate global perspectives more thoroughly into teacher preparation programs [7], the practical aspects of preparing pre-service teachers for the complexities of GCE remain underexplored. This lack of systematic integration leaves pre-service teachers without the tools to confidently address global issues in their future teaching. In addition, the rise of the digital age has brought new dimensions to GCE, with digital citizenship becoming increasingly relevant. Pre-service teachers must not only develop cultural and global competencies but also be equipped to teach digital literacy and self-efficacy as part of responsible global citizenship [8]. Digital citizenship is vital for engaging with global issues in today's interconnected world, as it shapes how individuals access information and interact with global communities [9]. However, there is limited research on how pre-service teachers develop these digital skills alongside their understanding of GCE, creating another critical gap in teacher preparation. Furthermore, cultural competence remains a central aspect of GCE, with pre-service teachers needing to understand and navigate cultural diversity in their classrooms [10]. This competence goes beyond curriculum content, encompassing the principles and practices of educational institutions to ensure that global citizenship values are not only taught but also embodied in teaching methods and environments [11].

This study examines pre-service teachers' perspectives regarding their knowledge, attitudes, abilities, and perceived challenges related to GCE. While previous research has explored the importance of integrating global perspectives into teacher preparation programs, the practical aspects of how pre-service teachers develop these competencies remain under-investigated. By addressing these gaps, this study aims to assess how well-prepared pre-service teachers are to implement GCE and highlight areas where teacher training programs can improve to support future educators in fostering global citizenship in their classrooms.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, incorporating qualitative and quantitative research paradigms. This strategy enhances the validity of the research findings by triangulating data sources, which helps in identifying both convergence and divergence between qualitative and quantitative results [12]. The approach is designed to evaluate pre-service teachers' perspectives on GCE at the North Eastern Mindanao State University (NEMSU)-Tandag Campus. The framework systematically collects and analyzes observational data while thoroughly investigating attitudes and perceptions related to GCE. To ensure the reliability and relevance of the data collection tools, the researcher developed questionnaires that were validated by subject matter experts, confirming their alignment with the study's objectives.

2.2. Research participants

The study included the pre-service teachers currently enrolled in the career and technical education (CTE) programs at NEMSU-Main Campus. A total of 239 pre-service teachers at NEMSU-Main Campus are nearing the completion of their teacher education program during the second semester of the academic year 2023–2024. The researcher employed stratified sampling to establish the sample size of 150 pre-service teachers, or roughly 60% of the 239 overall population. According to statistical recommendations, a sample size of at least 30% is required for trustworthy educational research; hence, this size is appropriate [13]. The selection process deliberately included pre-service teachers from diverse backgrounds, experiences, and educational environments, ensuring a range of perspectives on GCE were collected. Every individual involved was given a pseudonym to protect their identity. Consequently, the study established a secure setting that encourages transparent communication. These measures uphold the integrity of the research process by promoting transparent communication.

2.3. Research instrument

The study employed researchers made survey questionnaire. A panel of experts, comprising two GCE advocates, two faculty members with GCE expertise, the dean of the College of Teacher Education, and two pre-service teachers, validated the instrument's validity. The varied group ensured the questionnaire appropriately examined the targeted components connected to GCE and reflected the study's goals. After the instruments were validated, the dean of the general teacher training (GTT) officially authorized the study to begin. The NEMSU-Main Campus CTE Department, which served as the study site, had 239 pre-service teachers enrolled for the current academic year. Among these, 150 students, representing at least 60% of the total population, participated in the study as responders. As to the instrument reliability, Cronbach's alpha was used; the results showed a coefficient of 0.87, indicating strong internal consistency. This outcome shows that the questionnaire successfully assesses pre-service teachers' understanding of the concepts associated with

GCE, guaranteeing the validity and reliability of the data gathered for analysis. The study guaranteed diverse representation among pre-service teachers and control for confounding variables. Clear definitions kept the study's objectives front and center, and expert validation of the questionnaire reduced biases.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Knowledge about GCE

3.1.1. GCE concept familiarity

The findings revealed that 82 participants reported being moderately familiar with GCE, indicating a lesser familiarity and understanding of the concept. Additionally, 39 respondents were highly familiar with GCE, suggesting a more profound comprehension and active engagement with its ideas and goals. Lastly, 29 participants indicated they were slightly familiar with GCE, pointing to a basic understanding but with room for further exploration and development.

This variation in familiarity highlights the uneven distribution of GCE knowledge among pre-service teachers. While a significant number of participants have a solid understanding, there is a notable proportion with only a lesser familiarity. Similar to the findings of Rakisheva and Xu [14] teachers often exhibit limited familiarity with GCE concepts. Online discussions about global issues can enhance pre-service teachers' critical thinking and social justice awareness, suggesting that structured dialogue can foster a deeper understanding of GCE concepts [5]. These findings underscore the need for targeted educational strategies to enhance GCE understanding across all levels. Addressing these discrepancies through comprehensive training and resources could help standardize and deepen pre-service teachers' engagement with GCE, ultimately strengthening their ability to incorporate global citizenship principles into their future teaching practices.

3.1.2. Awareness of GCE

The findings reveal varying priorities among respondents regarding key concepts of GCE. The 25 respondents underscored the importance of raising awareness and acknowledging the need to educate citizens about global challenges. 30 participants emphasized promoting intercultural empathy and respect, stressing the significance of fostering mutual understanding across diverse cultures. Similarly, 35 participants highlighted the importance of developing critical thinking skills, particularly the ability to analyze complex global issues. Twenty respondents focused on the concept of justice, indicating a commitment to promoting equity and protecting human rights. Additionally, 26 participants stressed the importance of active citizenship, reflecting a strong dedication to civic engagement and contributing to positive societal change. The 11 participants prioritized sustainability, demonstrating a growing recognition of ecological issues and a commitment to responsible stewardship of the environment. Meanwhile, 3 participants chose not to respond.

These results are supported by studies such as Akaydın and Eşme [15], which found that pre-service teachers demonstrate high levels of environmental ethics awareness and positive attitudes toward sustainability, aligning with the 11 respondents who prioritized this theme in the current study. Similarly, Waghid [5] they were reported that pre-service teachers developed increased awareness of social justice, critical thinking, and empathy through online discussions on GCE, which corresponds to the 30 respondents in this study who emphasized intercultural empathy and the 20 who focused on justice.

The variation in emphasis among these GCE principles suggests opportunities for targeted interventions in the teacher education curriculum. As noted by Bano and Hina [16], integrating GCE and education for sustainable development into teacher preparation programs can help future educators become facilitators of global citizenship. To address the diverse focus areas observed in this study, curriculum improvements that foster a comprehensive understanding of these principles are crucial. Ensuring that pre-service teachers can effectively incorporate GCE concepts into their teaching will help develop globally competent and socially responsible educators.

3.2. Attitudes towards global citizenship

3.2.1. Extent of educators' responsibility to promote global citizenship among students

The results reveal a near-unanimous consensus among respondents regarding the role of educators in promoting global citizenship. Out of 150 participants, 139 respondents strongly agreed with the statement, "Educators have a complete obligation to encourage global citizenship among students." In comparison, the remaining 11 participants also agreed that educators are obligated to foster students' global citizenship. This indicates that every participant strongly believed that educators should actively promote cultivating a global citizenship mindset among pupils.

The unanimous agreement among respondents underscores the strong emphasis on GCE in teacher training programs. All participants believed educators have a crucial role in cultivating global citizenship, reflecting a collective commitment among future educators to integrate global awareness, critical thinking, and responsibility into their teaching practices. As noted by Lilang [17], which highlights the significance of

integrating GCE into teacher preparation to foster educators dedicated to promoting global awareness and responsibility in classrooms. Additionally, this result aligns with Cabello *et al.* [18], which emphasizes the role of teaching sustainable citizenship within teacher education programs. The commitment shown by pre-service teachers in this study indicates a recognition of the importance of proactive engagement in addressing global challenges, fostering intercultural empathy, and nurturing responsible global citizens. This collective recognition among respondents aligns with the broader goals of GCE, ensuring that future educators are prepared to embed global citizenship principles in their educational practices.

3.2.2. Importance of developing intercultural competence and awareness of global issues

The data revealed that 148 out of 150 participants rated the development of intercultural competency and comprehension of global concerns as “very important,” showing a strong consensus among pre-service teachers on the critical role of these skills in their future teaching careers. Only two participants rated this as “significant,” indicating a minor divergence from the prevailing perspective. This results align with the findings of Bayyurt and Yalçın [19], which emphasizes the need to integrate intercultural citizenship education into teacher training programs to equip future educators with the necessary skills to foster global citizenship and intercultural communication. The strong agreement among pre-service teachers reflects the increasing relevance of these competencies in a world that is growing more interconnected and diverse. Additionally, as noted by Lash *et al.* [20] enhancing intercultural competence through exposure to diverse cultural contexts and teaching experiences leads to improved sensitivity and a more remarkable ability to interpret cultural phenomena. The slight divergence, where two participants rated intercultural competency as “significant” rather than “very important,” may reflect varying levels of exposure or engagement with global education concepts. Nonetheless, the agreement underscores the need for teacher education programs to prioritize these competencies as essential for preparing globally competent educators.

3.3. Skills related to global citizenship

3.3.1. Ability confidence to integrate global perspectives into classroom teaching

The survey data reveals varying confidence levels among pre-service teachers in incorporating global viewpoints into their classroom teaching. Of the 150 participants, 94 reported feeling “slightly confident,” suggesting that a significant portion of respondents lack strong confidence in integrating global perspectives. Meanwhile, 43 individuals expressed “moderate confidence,” indicating some assurance but recognizing that their skills in this area could be further developed. Only 13 participants reported being “very confident” in incorporating global viewpoints, suggesting a relatively small number of pre-service teachers feel fully prepared to address global issues in their teaching.

These findings indicate that most pre-service teachers may feel inadequately prepared to incorporate global perspectives, pointing to a potential gap in their teacher training. The fact that 63% of respondents reported being only “slightly confident” suggests a need for targeted interventions in GCE to strengthen their preparedness. This result is consistent with Andrews and Aydin [21] which emphasizes the necessity for enhanced GCE training to boost pre-service teachers’ confidence in integrating global topics into their future classrooms.

The relatively low number of participants who reported being “very confident” (13) raises concern, highlighting an area where additional support and resources are critically needed. As noted by López and Pu [22], the integration of global perspectives and intercultural competencies into teacher education programs is essential for developing educators capable of addressing the demands of a globalized world. This gap may stem from limited exposure to global topics in the curriculum or a lack of practical teaching experiences that encourage the integration of global viewpoints. Addressing this gap is crucial to ensuring pre-service teachers are fully equipped to foster global citizenship in their students.

The “moderate confidence” expressed by 43 respondents reflects some progress but still leaves room for improvement. As supported by Kwon [23], moderate confidence in GCE is not uncommon among pre-service teachers, indicating that while they may have some foundational understanding, more structured support is needed to build their confidence fully. Enhancing professional development opportunities, particularly in global issue integration, intercultural teaching, and diverse field experiences, could bridge this gap and foster a more globally aware teaching force.

3.3.2. Preparedness in facilitating discussions on global issues and encouraging critical thinking among students

The survey results reveal a mixed sentiment among pre-service teachers regarding their readiness to promote discussions on global issues and foster critical thinking. Of the 150 respondents, 101 rated their confidence as neutral, indicating uncertainty or hesitation in their preparedness. In contrast, 43 participants expressed moderate confidence, while six respondents reported being highly confident in their ability to address

global topics in the classroom. These findings suggest a general uncertainty among pre-service teachers about their readiness to facilitate global discussions. This aligns with Smith *et al.* [24], which highlights similar hesitance and lack of preparedness. The high number of neutral responses indicates a potential gap in current training programs, indicating a need for more targeted support and interventions.

Effective teacher training, mainly through dialogic learning, can enhance confidence and readiness [24]. This underscores the need for comprehensive training programs focused on GCE. Furthermore, Man-Ho [25] highlights the importance of preparing educators for future uncertainties by transforming learning environments. Providing increased opportunities for exposure to GCE and fostering critical thinking skills could bridge this gap and better equip future educators to engage with global issues in their classrooms.

3.4. Perceived needs for GCE

3.4.1. Challenges in integrating global citizenship themes into your future teaching practice

Establish pre-service training programs, including extensive instruction on global concerns, cultural sensitivity, and intercultural communication proficiency. To expand their viewpoints, integrate case studies, guest lecturers, and practical learning opportunities. A significant challenge in integrating GCE into teaching practice is the absence of GCE-focused content within existing curricula, which makes incorporating global perspectives into instructional methods difficult. Advocates suggest curriculum modifications or additions are necessary to fully embed GCE into teaching practices. This aligns with the findings of Kopish [26], who emphasizes that providing pre-service teachers with appropriate resources and training is crucial for adapting existing curricula to include global viewpoints.

In addition to curriculum modifications, there is a critical need for sufficient resources. Pre-service teachers often face difficulties accessing adequate instructional materials and technologies that support integrating global citizenship topics into their teaching. Creating resource repositories, online platforms, and collaborative networks specifically designed for pre-service teachers can help address this gap by providing access to instructional materials, lesson plans, and multimedia resources related to GCE. Moreover, partnerships with educational institutions, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and global initiatives can facilitate access to low-cost or freely available materials.

Resistance from stakeholders, including administrators, parents, and community members, also poses a barrier to incorporating GCE concepts into the curriculum. Divergent views on the importance or appropriateness of GCE can hinder efforts to integrate these themes. To overcome this resistance, advocacy and awareness campaigns are essential to educate stakeholders on the significance of GCE in preparing students for an increasingly diverse and interconnected world. These campaigns should promote open dialogue, address concerns, and emphasize the professional, academic, and personal benefits of fostering global competency.

Another challenge lies in assessing students' understanding of GCE themes, as traditional assessment methods may not capture the full extent of students' critical thinking and engagement with global issues. Alternative assessment methods, such as project-based assessments, reflective journals, simulations, and peer evaluations, are recommended to address this. These approaches allow for a more comprehensive evaluation of student's analytical abilities and their capacity to apply GCE concepts to real-world situations. Offering targeted training to pre-service teachers on designing and implementing these assessment strategies is essential for effective GCE instruction.

3.4.2. Resources or support in enhancing the capacity to teach global citizenship effectively

Professional development workshops should offer access to workshops focusing on intercultural discussion, teaching global citizenship, and cultural competency. These workshops should give pre-service teachers valuable insights, techniques, and resources. Which aligned with the study of Tufail [27] they are stated that workshops on GCE have shown to be effective in enhancing faculty members' understanding and integration of GCE into curricula. The mentorship programs match pre-service teachers with experienced educators with specialized knowledge in GCE. These mentors provide personalized guidance, support, and practical advice. Additionally, it is essential to have curriculum guides and lesson plans that are thorough and pre-prepared, particularly tailored for teaching global citizenship topics. These resources are beneficial as they streamline the lesson preparation and offer a clear framework. Additionally, by participating in online communities, forums, or social media groups specifically focused on GCE, pre-service teachers may establish connections with fellow educators, collaborate on resource sharing, and exchange ideas.

Furthermore, the availability of a wide range of instructional materials, such as books, articles, films, multimedia resources, and authentic cultural artifacts, can enhance the quality of lesson plans and activities for pre-service teachers. Additionally, it is essential to provide pre-service teachers with experiential learning opportunities, such as study abroad programs, cultural immersion experiences, service-learning initiatives, or virtual exchange programs. These possibilities serve to enhance their comprehension of global challenges and cultures. The sixth factor is a Supportive School atmosphere, which refers to creating an atmosphere in schools where administrators, coworkers, and mentors highly value and prioritize GCE. This environment promotes

cooperation, creativity, and ongoing professional development. In addition, funding opportunities provide access to financial resources such as grants, scholarships, or stipends for professional development, travel, or the acquisition of instructional materials. These measures can help overcome financial obstacles and empower aspiring teachers to engage in projects related to teaching global citizenship. Additionally, professional development programs can target specific areas for improvement and identify challenges by using feedback, evaluation mechanisms, and assessments that assess the proficiency of aspiring teachers in teaching global citizenship topics.

3.5. Barriers to the education of global citizenship

The study revealed several significant barriers to implementing GCE, including systemic institutional obstacles, the absence of dedicated GCE courses or modules, insufficient support and resources for integration into curricula and practicum experiences, and resistance or indifference from faculty and administrators. This resistance, as noted by Ali [28], often stems from a lack of understanding or prioritization of GCE, resulting in limited institutional backing. Moreover, the absence of specific GCE coursework, as highlighted by Suryandari *et al.* [29] restricts students' exposure and engagement with global perspectives, complicating efforts to embed these concepts into existing curricula. In the current study, participants frequently identified these barriers, with a substantial number expressing concerns about the inadequate support for GCE within their institutions. This aligns with previous findings that institutional resistance and lack of resources create challenges for the effective integration of GCE. To address these issues, institutions need to take a proactive role in promoting GCE, not only within pre-service teacher education programs but also across the broader student body. Initiatives such as curriculum reforms, faculty training, and developing dedicated GCE modules could help overcome these barriers, ensuring a more robust integration of global citizenship principles into education.

4. CONCLUSION

Recent observations suggest that pre-service teachers engage with GCE at varying levels, with differences in familiarity, awareness, and readiness to incorporate global perspectives into teaching practices. Our findings provide conclusive evidence that while many participants are moderately familiar with GCE, a significant portion only possess basic understanding, signaling the need for enhanced educational strategies. The study reveals that respondents prioritize different GCE aspects, underscoring the necessity for a more integrated and comprehensive approach within teacher education programs. The consensus on the importance of developing intercultural competence and understanding global issues highlights these skills' critical role in preparing future educators. However, mixed confidence levels in integrating global perspectives into classroom teaching indicate gaps in current teacher training. These findings point to the need for targeted professional development and systemic changes to address barriers at institutional and policy levels. The study suggests that teacher education programs must incorporate comprehensive GCE training, offer professional development opportunities, and foster supportive environments prioritizing global citizenship.

Further research may explore the methods that most effectively enhance pre-service teachers' confidence in teaching global issues. Additionally, investigating how professional development programs impact readiness for GCE integration and identifying strategies to overcome institutional challenges could provide valuable insights. Expanding studies to include diverse educational contexts and geographic regions may offer a broader understanding of GCE integration and its effectiveness in different settings.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank North Eastern Mindanao State University and acknowledge the University President, Dr. Nemesio G. Loayon, PhD, for his undying support in finishing this study; and to the Department of General Teacher Training of this institution.

FUNDING INFORMATION

This research received no funding from any government, commercial, or non-profit organizations, and was conducted independently without financial support from external grants or sponsors.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Erwin B. Berry	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Rose-ann Sanchez		✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
Lozada-Calihat														

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

There are no declared conflicts of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

Informed consent was obtained from all individuals involved in the study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The pre-service teachers were assured they could freely participate, with their permission and independence fully recognized. After collecting the data, the researcher employed frequency distribution analysis to examine and evaluate the responses, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the pre-service teachers' perspectives on the GCE. This methodological approach utilizes a combination of different research methodologies and ensures ethical standards. It allows the study to gather valuable data on the acceptance and effectiveness of GCE among pre-service teachers at NEMSU-Main Campus. This data will significantly impact the development of future teacher education courses and instructional methods.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [EBB], upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. González-Valencia, M. M. Sabater, and A. S. Fernández, "Critical global citizenship education: a study on secondary school students," in *Frontiers in Education*, May 2022, vol. 7, p. 867113, doi: 10.3389/educ.2022.867113.
- [2] J.-L. Parejo, B. A. Lomotey, M. Reynés-Ramon, and M.-O. Cortón-Heras, "Professional development perspectives on global citizenship education in Ghana," *Educational Research*, vol. 64, no. 4, pp. 407–423, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1080/00131881.2022.2135120.
- [3] I. M. McGregor, "Teaching for global citizenship: a case study on the challenges of implementing a human rights course," *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 350–367, Apr. 2025, doi: 10.1080/03057925.2023.2254220.
- [4] M. Kwon, "A study on global citizenship and global citizenship education competency in pre-service teachers," *Society for International Cultural Institute*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 157–183, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.34223/jic.2023.16.1.157.
- [5] Z. Waghid, "Cultivating critical thinking, social justice awareness and empathy among pre-service teachers through online discussions on global citizenship education," *Journal of Creative Communications*, vol. 19, no. 1, 2024, doi: 10.1177/09732586231194438.
- [6] E. Saperstein, "Global citizenship education starts with teacher training and professional development," *Journal of Global Education and Research*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 125–139, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.5038/2577-509X.4.2.1121.
- [7] H. Aydin, U. Ogurlu, K. Andrew, A. R. Masalimova, E. M. Dorozhkin, and A. A. Malygin, "High school students' perceptions of global citizenship in central public high schools: implications for teacher educators," *Revista de Cercetare si Interventie Sociala*, vol. 65, pp. 187–205, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.33788/rcis.65.12.
- [8] C. Ç. Kansu and Y. Öksüz, "The Perception and level of digital citizenship on pre-service classroom teachers," *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 67–77, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.11114/jets.v7i10.4443.
- [9] N. Meekaeaw and P. Jongnimitsatoporn, "How capable are they of Becoming a digital teacher? Correlation analysis of individual characteristics, digital self-efficacy, and digital citizenship among pre-service teachers in Northeast Thailand," *Higher Education Studies*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 63–73, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.5539/hes.v13n2p63.
- [10] K. Halbert, "Global citizenship in teacher education: a critical framing and Australian curriculum case study," *ZEP – Zeitschrift für internationale Bildungsforschung und Entwicklungspädagogik*, vol. 2018, no. 4, pp. 15–19, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.31244/zep.2018.04.04.
- [11] M. Lourenço, "From caterpillars to butterflies: exploring pre-service teachers' transformations while navigating global citizenship education," in *Frontiers in Education*, Apr. 2021, vol. 6, p. 651250, doi: 10.3389/educ.2021.651250.
- [12] R. Adhikari and T. P. Timsina, "An educational study focused on the application of mixed method approach as a research method," *OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 94–109, 2024, doi: 10.3126/ocejmstss.v3i1.62229.

An examination of global citizenship education from the perspective of pre-service teachers (Erwin B. Berry)

- [13] L. Cohen, L. Manion, and K. Morrison, *Research methods in education*. London: Routledge, 2017, doi: 10.4324/9781315456539.
- [14] A. Rakisheva and L. Xu, "Pre-service teachers' perceptions on global citizenship and online education in a virtual exchange context," *Journal of Comparative & International Higher Education*, vol. 15, no. 5(S), pp. 54–63, 2024, doi: 10.32674/jcihe.v15i5(S).5895.
- [15] B. B. Akaydin and A. Eşme, "Investigation of pre-service teachers' environmental ethics awareness and attitudes towards sustainable environment," *Anadolu Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 704–726, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.34056/aujef.1288972.
- [16] N. Bano and K. Hina, "Inclusion of global citizenship education and sustainable development in pre-service curriculum: a perspective study," *International Journal of Innovation in Teaching and Learning (IJITL)*, vol. 6, no. 2, 2021, doi: 10.35993/ijitl.v6i2.855.
- [17] J. Lilang, "Master teachers in public secondary schools: their journey towards integration and contextualization of global citizenship into Araling Panlipunan curriculum and instruction," *Romblon State University Research Journal*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 63–70, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.58780/rsurj.v6i1.174.
- [18] V. Cabello, C. G. Zúñiga, C. A. Valbuena, F. Manrique, M. J. Albarrán, and A. Moncada-Arce, "We are not being taught sustainable citizenship!," *LUMAT: International Journal on Math, Science and Technology Education*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 18–49, May 2024, doi: 10.31129/LUMAT.12.2.2135.
- [19] Y. Bayyurt and Ş. Yalçın, "Intercultural citizenship and pre-service teacher education," *Journal of English as a Lingua Franca*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 105–115, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1515/jelf-2022-2072.
- [20] M. Lash, S. M. Akpovo, and K. Cushner, "Developing the intercultural competence of early childhood preservice teachers: preparing teachers for culturally diverse classrooms," *Journal of Early Childhood Teacher Education*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 105–126, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1080/10901027.2020.1832631.
- [21] K. Andrews and H. Aydın, "Pre-service teachers' perceptions of global citizenship education in the social studies curriculum," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2020, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 84–113, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3549266.
- [22] M. M. López and C. Pu, "Infusing Global perspectives into teacher education: a self-study from Texas and Georgia," in *People-Centered Approaches Toward the Internationalization of Higher Education*, G. Malfatti, Ed., Hershey, PA: IGI Global, 2021, pp. 20–45, doi: 10.4018/978-1-7998-3796-1.ch002.
- [23] M. Kwon, "The comparison of global citizenship and global citizenship competency between pre-service early childhood education teachers and pre-service special education teachers," *Democracy and Peace Institute, Chosun University*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 25–52, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.55082/jdp.2023.6.2.25.
- [24] B. Smith, J. Y. Neoh, A. McDowall, and E.-J. A. Kim, "Preparing teachers for critical global and democratic practice: shifting inquiries into the teaching of democracy and global citizenship in teacher education," *Curriculum Perspectives*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 525–536, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s41297-024-00235-0.
- [25] A. L. Man-Ho, "Re-envisioning the learning landscape: equipping our students with uncertainty preparedness for the future world of crises," *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 692–705, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1080/02188791.2023.2231643.
- [26] M. A. Kopish, "Preparing future global citizenship educators: navigating a contested field from theory to practice," in *Discourses of Globalisation, Active Citizenship and Education*, J. Zajda and A. Rapoport, Eds., Cham: Springer, 2024, pp. 69–97, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-55493-3_5.
- [27] M. Tufail, "Professional development workshop on global citizenship education experiences of university teachers," *Siazga Research Journal*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 66–75, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.58341/srj.v3i1.45.
- [28] R. Ali, "How challenging? Barriers for teachers in institutional implementation of blended learning," *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 324–341, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.1080/02680513.2024.2342922.
- [29] K. C. Suryandari, R. Rokhmaniyah, and W. Wahyudi, "Perspectives of students and teachers form continuing professional development: challenge and obstacle," *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 2310–2319, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.35445/alishlah.v16i2.4572.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Erwin B. Berry is an associate professor II in the Department of General Teacher Training and is currently the director for Research and Development at North Eastern Mindanao State University. He finished his doctorate in educational management at Eulogio Amang Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology. In 2014, he received his master's degree in administration and supervision from Metro Manila College. He graduated with a bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science Cumlaude from Surigao State College of Technology now Surigao Del Norte State University. He is a recipient of the 2018 Korea-Philippine Teacher Exchange at Tanhyon Middle School in South Korea. He published a research article entitled inquiry-based and differentiated instruction in electromagnetic wave grounded on the triarchic theory of intelligence, and a book entitled science, technology and society and a simple approach in teaching social research. He can be contacted at email: eberry@nemsu.edu.ph.

Rose-ann Sanchez Lozada-Calihah was born on March 6, 1992, in Tago, Surigao del Sur, and currently residing in Sumo-sumo, Tago, Surigao del Sur. She is married to Nerie John Rivera Calihat. She completed her bachelor's degree in elementary education at North Eastern Mindanao State University in 2012, earned her master's in educational management in 2018, and pursue her doctor of education. She is a master teacher 1 at Sumo-sumo Elementary School, Tago District, Surigao del Sur Division. She had been teaching since 2013. Previously, she taught kindergarten for 11 years and now handling grade 3 classes. She is passionate about journalism and badminton, always aiming to inspire her students through dedication and leadership. She can be contacted at email: roseannlozada23@gmail.com.